

Transannular Electronic Interactions of some Cyclobutane Derivatives

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One of the advantages of the molecular orbital theory over early resonance theory is that the former readily accounts for certain electronic interactions between groups which are not conjugated in the classical sense. The purpose of this paper is to describe the syntheses of four cyclobutane derivatives I, II, III and IV and to discuss their unusual ultraviolet absorption spectra which have been determined in ethanol. They all show unusual ultraviolet absorption spectra which have been attributed to transannular electronic interactions. The molecular model constructions of these compounds show the π -orbitals of the transannularly situated chromophores—two carbonyl and two azomethines can come closer to each other cross-wise because of the folded conformation. This is an interesting consequence of the stereochemistry of the four-membered ring. The origin of π - π^* transition (K-band) and its assignments are discussed from the standpoint of the transannular electronic interactions (Transannular Conjugation).

BY using cyclohexanecarbonyl chloride (Eastman Kodak Co.) as starting material, Dispiro [5·1·5·1] tetradecane-7,14-dione I and Dispiro [5·1·5·1] tetradecane-7,14-dioxime II were prepared (Fig. 1). Using Isobutyryl chloride (Eastman Kodak Co.) as starting material, 2,2,4,4-tetramethyl-1,3-cyclo-butanedione III and 2,2,4,4-tetramethyl-1,3-cyclo-butanedione dioxime IV were synthesized (Fig. 2).

Experimental

Dispiro [5·1·5·1] tetradecane-7, 14-dione¹ I :

A 500 ml, three-necked, round bottom flask is equipped with a mechanical stirrer, a condenser, a dropping funnel, and a nitrogen inlet. The flask is charged with a solution of cyclohexanecarbonyl chloride (30g, 0.2505 mole) in 250 ml of dry benzene, the system is flushed with nitrogen, and a nitrogen atmosphere is maintained thereafter. In the dropping funnel is placed anhydrous triethylamine (35g, 0.35 mole), which is added to the stirred reaction mixture dropwise (approx. 30 minutes). The mixture is brought to reflux and refluxing is continued (with stirring) 18-20 hours. The cooled solution is then filtered to remove triethylamine hydrochloride, and the filtrate is transferred to a separatory funnel and washed with 200 ml 5% aqueous hydrochloric acid

followed by an equal volume of water. The organic solution is dried by sodium sulfate, the benzene is removed (rotary evaporator), and the residue is recrystallized from petroleum ether-ethanol. The weight of the product thus obtained is about 12g (54%), mp 161-162°. The ultraviolet absorption spectra show $\lambda_m=204$ nm with $\epsilon_m=810$ and $\lambda_m=234$ nm with $\epsilon_m=180$ in 95% ethanol (Fig. 1).

2,2,4,4-Tetramethyl-1, 3-Cyclodecanedione¹ III :

Similarly using the above procedure, 2,2,4,4-tetramethyl-1,3-cyclo-butanedione was prepared by using isobutyryl chloride as the starting material. The melting point of the compound is 113-114° (Cf 113-115°). The ultraviolet absorption spectra show $\lambda_m=204$ nm with $\epsilon_m=145$ and $\lambda_m=226$ nm with $\epsilon_m=120$ in 95% ethanol (Fig. 2).

Dispiro [5·1·5·1] tetradecane-7, 14-dioxime² II :

Dispiro [5·1·5·1] tetradecane-7, 14-dione (5g) was treated with 10g of hydroxylamine hydrochloride, 20g of potassium hydroxide, and 80 ml of 95% ethanol. The mixture was heated under reflux for 24 hours and poured into 500 ml of water. The suspension was stirred and allowed to stand to permit unchanged ketone to separate.

Fig. 1. Preparation of Dispiro [5.1.5.1] Tetradecane-7, 14-dioxime.

Fig. 2. Preparation of 2,2,4,4-tetramethyl-1,3-cyclobutanedione dioxime

The solution filtered, acidified with hydrochloric acid and allowed to stand to permit the oxime to crystallize. The product was recrystallized from ethanol or an ethanol-water mixture. The yield was 80%. The melting point of the oxime II is 235°. The infrared absorption shows the right frequency for the oxime group. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum shows $\lambda_m = 212 \text{ nm}$ with $\epsilon_m = 2200$ in 95% ethanol (Fig. 1). The elemental analysis, calculated for $C_{14}N_2O_2H_{22}$: C, 67.20%; H, 8.80%; N, 11.20%; Found C, 67.25%; H, 8.78%; N, 11.15%.

2,2,4,4-Tetramethyl-1,3-Cyclobutanedione dioxime² IV :

Similarly using the above procedure, 2,2,4,4-tetramethyl-1,3-cyclobutanedione dioxime was prepared by using 2,2,4,4-tetramethyl-1,3-cyclobutanedione as the starting material. The yield of the compound IV was 85%. The melting point of the oxime IV is 269-270° and is uncorrected. The infrared absorption shows the right frequency for the oxime group. The ultraviolet absorption spectrum shows $\lambda_m = 206 \text{ nm}$ with $\epsilon_m = 6000$ in 95% ethanol (Fig. 2). The elemental analysis, calculated for $C_8N_2O_2H_{14}$: C, 56.47%; H, 8.24%; N, 16.47%; Found: C, 56.55%; H, 8.34%; N, 16.35%.

Discussion

Cyclobutane Conformation :

Cyclobutane exists in planar and nonplanar conformations. Thermodynamic and spectroscopic studies show the cyclobutane and many of its derivatives exist predominantly in a "butterfly" conformation or folded conformation⁶. The dihedral angle between the two wings of the bent ring is

Fig. 3 π -Orbitals Cross-Wise Interaction

about 25° deviated from the planarity. This folding increases the angle strain of cyclobutane from 90° to 88°, but allows for a greater relief of torsional strain⁴ (Fig. 3). There are different folded forms of cyclobutane—a mixture of rapidly oscillating nonplanary conformers. At room temperature, thermal energy causes these forms to be interconverted rapidly⁴ (Fig. 4).

In planar form of cyclobutane and its derivatives all the CH_2 groups are in eclipsed conformation. Cyclobutane has more eclipsed C-H nonbonded repulsions, due to this, to reach a more stable level, the planar ring folds slightly and vibrates through the plane⁵ (Fig. 4). The folding of the ring (to about 150-160° from the planar, 180°) relieves the eclipsing by allowing an approach to a staggered conformation of the C-H bonds around the ring⁵.

In nonplanar cyclobutane conformation, the substituents are probably most favorably located in what might be called the less hindered, "Quasi-equatorial positions⁶." The energy of eclipsing the hydrogens in cyclobutane is sufficient to cause the ring to be nonplanar⁶. The cyclobutane ring is most likely to be nonplanar. The nonplanar structure is the most stable.

Transannular Interactions :

The visible and ultraviolet absorption spectra of Dispiro [5'1'5'1] tetradecane-7,14-dione I, Dispiro [5'1'5'1] tetradecane-7,14-dioxime II, 2,2,4,4-tetramethyl-1,3-cyclobutanedione III and 2,2,4,4-tetramethyl-1,3-cyclobutanedione Dioxime IV have been measured in ethanol, and the compounds exhibit an unusual absorption bands. Dispiro [5'1'5'1] tetradecane-7, 14-dione exhibits an unusual absorption band at 204 nm with a molar absorptivity of 810 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹; dispiro [5'1'5'1] tetradecane-7, 14-dioxime shows band at 212 nm with a molar absorptivity of 2200 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹; 2,2,4,4-tetramethyl-1,3-cyclobutanedione shows band at 204 nm with a molar absorptivity of 145 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹; and 2,2,4,4-tetramethyl-1,3-cyclobutanedione dioxime shows band at 206 nm with a molar absorptivity of 6000 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. These unusual bands have been attributed to transannular electronic interactions.

Similar bands have been observed in the spectra of other related cyclobutane derivatives containing nonconjugated chromophores across the ring and have been attributed to transannular electronic interaction⁷, (Fig. 5).

Mechanism of Interaction :

These four compounds I, II, III and IV are cyclobutane derivatives. These compounds were chosen because of the favorable geometry for such interactions of the four-membered ring with diametrically opposed two similar functional groups. The folding of four-membered ring brings the

Fig. 4. Cyclobutane Derivative Rapid Transformations.

nonconjugated two $>C=O$ chromophores closer to each other cross-wise in the compounds I and III. Similarly the folding of the cyclobutane ring brings

Fig. 5. Transannular Interactions in Related Compounds.

the transannular two $>C=N$ —azomethine chromophores closer to each other cross-wise in the compounds II and IV. This permits the orientation of the π -orbitals of two $C=O$ chromophores of I and III and two $>C=N$ — chromophores of II and IV to come closer to each other in cross-wise manner and thus permit an effective overlap interaction of the π -orbitals (Fig. 3).

Such an orbital overlap gives rise to bonding and antibonding π -molecular orbitals which encompass both the chromophores. The band can then be

assigned to π - π^* transition (K-band). This K-band

results from π - π^* transition and are characterized by high absorptivity.

Transannular Interactions in Other Related Compounds⁷ :

A number of examples are listed in Table 1 where comparisons are made with similar transannular electronic interactions of nonconjugated compounds (Table 1).

There are cases where the $C=O$ and $C=C$ are nonconjugated in the classical sense but where

TABLE 1 COMPARISON OF SPECTRAL DATA FOR CYCLOBUTANE DERIVATIVES.

Compound	Solvent	λ_m, nm	ϵ_m
Dispiro [5.1.5.1] tetradecane-7,14-dione I	Ethanol	204	810
Dispiro [5.1.5.1] tetradecane-7,14-dioxime II	Ethanol	212	2200
2, 2, 4, 4-Tetramethyl-1, 3-cyclobutanedione III	Ethanol	204	145
2, 2, 4, 4-Tetramethyl-1, 3-Cyclobutanedione dioxime IV	Ethanol	206	6000
3-Methylenecyclobutanone ⁷ V	Ethanol	214	1500
Bicyclo [2.2.2] 5-Octen-2-one ⁷ VI	-	202	3000

interaction does occur to produce an absorption band⁷. The structures where this occurs, the $C=O$ and $C=C$ groups are oriented so that there can be effective overlap of the π -orbitals⁷. For example, 3-methylenecyclobutanone V shows a moderately strong band near 214 nm with a molar absorptivity of 1500 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹. Compound VI shows band near 202 nm with a molar absorptivity of 3000 liter mole⁻¹ cm⁻¹ (Fig. 5).

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